

<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.

Researching the Causes of Financial Fraud in Listed Companies: A Qualitative Comparative Analysis Based On the Fraud Triangle Theory Using Fuzzy Sets

Author's Details:

Yaqin Wang, Jian Cao

Abstract:

The advancement in science and technology, along with the complexity of macroeconomic circumstances, has contributed significantly to the challenge of identifying instances of corporate financial fraud. Against this backdrop, this paper explores the factors that induce companies to engage in fraudulent financial behavior. By utilizing the Fraud Triangle theory as a foundation, this analysis offers an in-depth examination from three aspects: pressure, opportunity, and rationalization. This study utilized the fsQCA (fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis) method to investigate the configuration of factors that influence financial fraud behavior. A sample was drawn from typical cases inspected by the China Securities Regulatory Commission from 2016 to 2022. It was found that individual factors have limited influence on fraudulent behavior and cannot solely cause fraudulent activities. The five common configurations leading to fraudulent behavior are opportunity-driven, weakly supervised, individual dominant, internal-external alliances, and pressure-driven. This research is imperative for preventing and identifying instances of financial fraud.

Keywords: Publicly-traded companies; Financial fraud; Fraud Triangle Theory; fsQCA.

1.Introduction

After the financial scandals of Enron and WorldCom, the U.S. Congress enacted the Sarbanes-Oxley Act in 2002, with the hope of leveraging auditors' role to reduce occurrences of financial fraud. Following the fraudulent cases of Yin Guoxiang and Guangxia Bank, China's Ministry of Finance issued the "Basic Norms for Enterprise Internal Control" in 2008, explicitly indicating the crucial role of internal control in preventing financial fraud incidents. Therefore, this article delves into the motives behind financial fraud behaviors, in order to better identify cases of such behavior in companies. Traditional analyses of financial fraud motives often exhibit bias towards results because there exists an interdependent and complementary relationship between the factors that encourage fraudulent behavior in corporations. Past research has unfortunately largely concentrated on the impact of individual factors on financial fraud events, with little attention paid to exploring cross-cutting connections between motivational factors. As a result, relying solely on researching the net effect of financial fraud motives may prove inadequate. For instance, attributing Luckin Coffee's fraudulent activities solely to financing pressures would seem inaccurate. With the increasing complexity of macroeconomic circumstances, cases such as LeEco's fraudulent activities over long periods of time and the mind-boggling "Mussels" incident have exposed how singular explanations for instances of financial fraud are often skewed and even contradictory at times. Therefore, building upon the foundation of the fraud triangle theory, this article employs the fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis

(fsQCA) method to explore the various combinations of factors that spur occurrences of financial fraud. By identifying the most probable path leading to instances of financial fraud, this study identifies characteristics typical of fraudulent cases in China's listed companies, providing valuable insights for identifying and preventing occurrences of financial fraud in the future.

2.Literature review and analytical framework

2.1 Literature review

The academic research on financial fraud began with an examination into the causative factors, and has since led to the formation of four dominant normative theories that possess strong theoretical frameworks at present. These theories include the Financial Fraud Iceberg Theory^[1], the Financial Fraud Triangle Theory^[2], the GONE Theory of financial fraud^[3], and the Financial Fraud Risk Factor Theory^[4]. Among these, the Fraud Triangle Theory was originally proposed by the distinguished American auditing scholar Lawrence Sawyer, and further developed by Albrecht, founder of the American Association of Certified Fraud Examiners. As one of the primary theories on the causality behind financial fraud, the theory has received significant recognition from both the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants and the Chinese Institute of Certified Public Accountants, and is presently applied in the latest auditing standards.

Furthermore, using the Fraud Triangle Theory as a foundation, Parlindungan, Ricardo, and Africano (2017)^[5] examined the likelihood of financial fraud in non-financial companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2008 to 2013, finding a close correlation between profitability and audits with financial fraud. Wu Zhongxin (2015)^[6] and others conducted research on agricultural listed companies punished for financial reporting fraud from 1993 to 2013 based on the Fraud Triangle Theory, discovering that limited professional competence and independence of certified public accountants provided opportunities for fraud. Lin Bin (2022)^[7] used questionnaire surveys based on the Fraud Triangle Theory, revealing that opportunity is the foremost factor in the occurrence of fraud, followed by rationalization as the secondary factor, and greed as the most prominent pressure factor.

2.2 Analytical framework

This article endeavors to create a quantitative analysis framework (Figure 1) that can measure the factors contributing to the occurrence of financial fraud, building upon the theoretical foundations of the Fraud Triangle Theory. The Fraud Triangle Theory ascribes the causative factors of financial fraud to three key components: pressure, opportunity, and rationalization.

This article endeavors to create a quantitative analysis framework (Figure 1) that can measure the factors contributing to the occurrence of financial fraud, building upon the theoretical foundations of the Fraud Triangle Theory. The Fraud Triangle Theory ascribes the causative factors of financial fraud to three key components: pressure, opportunity, and self rationalization.

Figure 1. A framework for analyzing the factors that impact financial fraud.

(1) Pressure

Pressure factors are the driving force behind fraudulent behavior in enterprises, mainly including financial pressure as well as personal and social pressures. Financial pressure is the most crucial catalyst that promotes fraudulent financial activities, which mainly arise from the dual pressure of profitability and debt repayment. Therefore, this paper chooses profit-making ability and debt repayment pressure as measures to gauge the "pressure" dimension. Based on the findings of Zhang Lijun and Luo Zhen (2008)^[8], who employed a clustering analysis approach to screen financial indicators, and taking into account the feasibility of actual operational processes, this paper investigates profitability by using the gross profit margin of the main business, and debt-repaying capacity by using the asset-liability ratio as the measuring criteria.

(2) Opportunity

The term 'opportunity factors' refers to the timing in which enterprises are capable of conducting financial fraud without getting caught or punished. From the perspective of fraudulent opportunities, we divide opportunity factors into three aspects. Firstly, a relatively low level of internal control is displayed in enterprises. For example, the manifestation of such low internal controls could be the lack of independence of internal audits from management, leading to problems with supervising management. Secondly, external audit lacks independence. According to Hogan Chris E (2008)^[9], auditing has a significant impact on the occurrence of financial fraud. Thirdly, the rule of law environment is critical. Based on Hu Haifeng's (2022)^[10] research on A-share listed companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen from 2004 to 2019, the rule of law has an important influence on corporate fraudulent behavior. In regions where the rule of law is well-established, a higher level of law enforcement, departmental independence, and efficiency increases the probability of discovering illegal behavior by enterprises. However, in areas with a relatively lower level of rule of law, the likelihood of detecting fraudulent activities is significantly reduced.

(3) Self rationalization.

The phenomenon of "self-rationalization" primarily stems from incorrect professional ethics, morals, and values held by corporations or individuals, and belongs to the realm of personal morality. Regarding the self-rationalizing factors in financial fraud causation, most cases have occurred due to the pursuit of self-interest maximization. However, there are exceptions as well. For instance, in the Luckin Coffee fraud case, the management did not act out of pure self-interest but to accomplish the company's strategic objectives. Hence, a simplistic view that solely focuses on greed would be inaccurate. Regardless of the motivation behind the actions of managers, the role of self-rationalization in fraudulent behavior is closely linked to the corporate governance structure and its equity mechanisms. Therefore, in order to quantify the dimension of self-rationalization and according to Yue Qian's (2016)^[11] research on the impact of unreasonable equity structures on corporate governance, this paper opts to use the governance structure of companies as a measure of self-rationalization.

3. Research Methods and Data Construction

3.1 Research Methods

This paper has selected the fsQCA method for analyzing the causation of financial fraud due to three primary reasons: Firstly, traditional regression analysis methods can only yield "net effects" of individual factors (Du and Jia, 2017)^[12]. Secondly, while there are other methods for studying configuration, they are incapable of identifying interdependence between conditions and causal asymmetry (Zhang and Du, 2019)^[13]. We elected to employ the fsQCA method to analyze the causation of financial fraud for three primary reasons: ① The conventional regression analysis method, as opined by Du Yunzhou and Jia Liangding (2017)^[12], solely furnishes the "net effect" of individual factors. ② Although research configuration methodologies are not confined to solely utilizing the QCA method, these alternatives fail to discern the interdependence between conditions and causal non-symmetry, as stated by Zhang Ming and Du Yunzhou (2019)^[13]. ③ Due

to the intricacy inherent in studying the catalysts behind financial fraud, the fsQCA method presents a more advantageous approach for detecting nuanced variations, as expounded by Rihoux and Ragin (2009)^[14].

3.2. Data Resource and Sample Selection

In order to explore the joint effects among the underlying causes that induce fraudulent financial behavior, this paper selects a representative sample of fraudulent companies disclosed by the China Securities Regulatory Commission (CSRC) between 2016 and 2022 as the research object. Due to the covert nature of fraudulent behavior, most of them may not be discovered and punished until years after the occurrence. Therefore, this paper calculates relevant indicators based on the average values within the fraud duration period of each enterprise, while selecting listed companies as the study sample to obtain more comprehensive data sources. Furthermore, in order to fully consider the regional disparities in the legal environment, this paper selects multiple provinces as the research objects. In addition, due to the stringent case selection criteria of fsQCA method which requires not only ensuring the complete homogeneity of the case groups to ensure comparable cases, but also maximizing the differences among the case groups (Qin and Yang, 2020)^[15], we have chosen a total of 60 listed companies as research samples, consisting of 30 representative fraudulent cases reported by the China Securities Regulatory Commission (CSRC) and their corresponding counterparts that are non-fraudulent but in the same industry. The detailed distribution of our sample can be illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Distribution of sample provinces

3.3. Variable Measuring

Table 1. Variable settings and data sources.

	Variable Type		Measurement index	Data Source
	Conditional variables	Pressure	Profitability(PF)	Main business margin
Debt repayment pressure(DP)			Debt Asset ratio	Annual report
Opportunity		Internal control(IC)	Internal Control Index	Dibo Database
		Lack of audit independence(LAI)	The duration of time collaborated with the firm	Annual report
		Legal environment(LE)	Legal environment	Chinese market-oriente

				d database
	Self rationalization	Governance structure(GS)	Stock right	Annual report
Outcome variable	Financial Fraud		Whether there is fraud	CSRC disclose

3.3.1 Conditional variables

The occurrence of financial fraud in a corporation can be influenced by many interconnected factors. To effectively analyze the effect of conditional variables, the fsQCA methodology is often used. Therefore, based on the fraud triangle theory and previous research, researchers have ultimately chosen six conditional variables to assess the most likely configurations that may result in financial fraudulent behavior.

Among these factors, pressure mainly comes from profitability (PF) and debt pressure (DP). Profitability (PF) primarily stems from the need for a business to generate profits. Data was collected by averaging the main business profit margins for the duration of fraudulent activity spanning from 2016 to 2022, which were disclosed by listed companies to the China Securities Regulatory Commission, providing an initial value for subsequent calibration. On the other hand, debt pressure (DP) refers to the financial burden faced by a corporation regarding its debts. Similar to profitability, the average asset-liability ratio during the fraudulent activities time frame provided an initial value for subsequent calibration.

Opportunities primarily encompass internal controls(IC), legal environment (LE), and lack of audit independence (LAI). Internal controls (IC) consist of various organizational, planning procedures and methods that are implemented by the board of directors, board of supervisors, management, and all employees to regulate and control business operations. The "Internal Control Index" collected from DiBao's internal control database is used to calculate the average value during the fraudulent period, providing an initial calibration value for subsequent analyses. Similarly, the legal environment (LE) is assessed through the market's ability to maintain its legal environment, with data gathered from the Chinese Marketization Index for companies during the fraudulent period being utilized as an initial calibration value. Lastly, a lack of audit independence (LAI) is assigned a value of 1 when a listed company cooperates with an accounting firm for more than three years. If this motivation is not present, LAI is valued at 0.

Self rationalization primarily encompasses governance structure (GS). Governance structure (GS) is closely related to the company's equity structure, and this article assesses the presence of a dominant shareholder as an indicator for evaluating corporate governance structure. If a company experiences problems with a dominant shareholder during its operations, it will be assigned a value of 1. If none of these motives exist, it will be valued at 0.

3.3.2 .Outcome variable

The occurrence of financial fraud (FF) is a dependent variable that is related to the cross-relationship between inducing factors for financial fraud behavior. This article evaluates whether a company engages in fraudulent behavior by assessing whether it has been publicly disclosed by the China Securities Regulatory Commission. If so, the company is given a value of 1; otherwise, it is valued at 0.

3.4. Data Calibration

After collecting the raw data, calibration is necessary. Following Fiss' (2011) [16] calibration method, the 75% is considered as a full membership value, the 50% is taken as the intermediate point, and the 25% is regarded as a full non-membership value. The specific calibration results can be found in Table 2.

Table 2.Measurement and calibration of variables

variables	Full Membershi p	Intermediate Point	Full Non-Membership
-----------	------------------------	--------------------	------------------------

Profitability (PF)	0.29	0.19	0.12
Debt pressure (DP)	0.66	0.51	0.36
Internal control(IC)	690.78	651.9	602.69
Legal environment(LE)	9.76	6.77	5.86

4.Data Analysis and Discussion of Results

4.1.Analysis of the necessitation of individual conditions

Before conducting configuration analysis, it is necessary to analyze the necessitation of single factors based on the requirements of qualitative comparative analysis using fuzzy sets. Generally speaking, a conditional variable can be considered a necessary condition for forming the resulting variable when its consistency index is >0.9 . Table 2 indicates that only the lack of audit independence (LAI) has a consistency index of 0.766667, which is not higher than the critical value, while the remaining indices are below the threshold. Therefore, it can be inferred that a single antecedent condition alone cannot lead to financial fraud. Since the conditional variable did not pass the consistency test, there is no need to further demonstrate the coverage index. The above results also indicate the weak explanatory power of a single conditional variable on the resulting variable, highlighting the importance of studying the configuration effect of the group on the outcome.

Table 3. Analysis of the Necessity of Single Factors

Conditions tested		FF		~FF	
		Consistency	Coverage	Consistency	Coverage
Pressure	PF	0.419333	0.438924	0.536067	0.561091
	~PF	0.580667	0.555857	0.463933	0.444125
	DP	0.571333	0.575941	0.420667	0.424059
	~DP	0.428667	0.425265	0.579333	0.575735
Opportunity	IC	0.397333	0.39301	0.613667	0.60699
	~IC	0.602667	0.60937	0.386333	0.39063
	LE	0.31	0.327937	0.635333	0.672073
	~LE	0.69	0.654235	0.364667	0.345765
Self rationalization	LAI	0.566667	0.425	0.766667	0.575
	~LAI	0.433333	0.65	0.233333	0.35
Self rationalization	GS	0.6	0.473684	0.666667	0.526316
	~GS	0.4	0.545455	0.333333	0.454545

4.2.Condition Configuration Analysis

This text undertook a truth table normalization analysis based on calibrated data before conducting conditional configuration analysis. With reference to Fiss's (2011) ^[16] research, this paper established the consistency level threshold at 0.8 and the case frequency threshold at 1 during the analytical process. Using the standard analytical process of qualitative comparative analysis software, this study analyzed the specific combination relationship of conditional variables known as configuration effect. Using fsQCA (3.0) software, the sufficiency of different configurations of six antecedent conditions, namely profitability (PF), debt pressure (DP), internal control (IC), legal environment (LE), lack of audit independence (LAI), and governance structure (GS), were analyzed. The resulting configuration patterns for the antecedent condition variables are presented in Table 4, where the consistency indicator of the solution is 0.9117. This value exceeds the critical value, usually set at 0.8, indicating that the empirical analysis of the sufficiency of conditional configurations is effective. The coverage indicator of the solution is 0.413, implying that these conditional configurations can explain 41.3% of financial fraud behaviors in listed companies. By

combining the intermediate solution and the parsimonious solution, we can effectively identify the core and peripheral conditions of specific conditional variable combinations. In general, the conditions present in both the intermediate and parsimonious solutions are called core conditions. Meanwhile, the conditions existing only in the intermediate solution are classified as auxiliary conditions.

Table 4. Analysis of financial fraud configurations

Conditions	opportunity-driven	weakly supervised	individual dominant	internal-external alliances	pressure-driven
PF	⊗	•	•	⊗	⊗
DP	•	•	•	•	⊗
IC	⊗	•	•	⊗	⊗
LE	•	⊗	•	⊗	⊗
LAI	⊗	⊗	⊗	•	⊗
GS	⊗	•	⊗	•	
Raw coverage	0.032	0.038	0.0426667	0.161667	0.094
Unique coverage	0.0183333	0.0216667	0.031	0.161667	0.0693333
Consistency	0.979592	0.876923	0.920863	0.877034	0.959184
Solution coverage	0.413				
Solution consistency	0.9117				

Note: If either • or • is presented, the condition exists. If ⊗ or ⊗ is indicated, the condition does not exist. • and • are core conditions while ⊗ and ⊗ are auxiliary ones.

4.3. Results and Discussion

(1) Opportunity-driven (~IC*LE*~LAI*~PF*DP*~GS)

Configuration 1 highlights the core conditions of a lawful environment, low internal control over enterprises, and lack of audit independence. Meanwhile, auxiliary conditions involve issues pertaining to corporate profitability, governance structure, and debt pressure. This depiction demonstrates that the efficiency of law enforcement can be greatly undermined by weak internal control and inadequate audit independence, even in regions with well-established law enforcement mechanisms. As corporations prioritize profit over ethical conduct, weaknesses in their governance structure and internal control catalyze fraudulent behavior. Furthermore, the absence of audit independence significantly reduces the chances of unearthing such deceitful actions. Thus, this configuration characterizes a prevalent variety of financial fraud tactic known as "opportunistic orientation." From a fraud triangle perspective, this approach hinges on subpar internal control quality and lack of adequate audit independence.

(2) Weakly supervised (PF*DP*~LAI*IC*~LE*GS)

In configuration 2, the core elements are debt pressure, decreased profitability, and a lack of audit independence. The auxiliary factors include issues with internal control and governance structure, as well as deficiencies in the legal system. This framework explains that financial fraud is not limited to poorly performing companies; successful "star" enterprises have also been known to engage in such illegal practices. For example, a company operating within this framework may have demonstrated strong financial performance with no outstanding debt or signs of dominance within its governance structure, boasting an impressive degree of internal controls. However, due to leniency within the external legal system, management could invariably view fraudulent activity as presenting no significant punishments if discovered. "The absence of audit independence leads accounting firms to abandon professional prudence and conspire with the corporation in fraudulent activities. This substantially decreases the likelihood of fraud detection, even when the firm has demonstrated successful past performance. From a risk-benefit perspective, within this configuration, fraudulent behavior can be justified as offering significant benefits for

management with minimal perceived costs. Both the lack of audit independence and issues with the legal environment pertain to the opportunity component of the fraud triangle theory. However, unlike in Configuration 1, these problems fall under external regulatory oversight. Accordingly, we refer to this configuration as the “Weakly supervised”.

(3) Individual dominant (DP*IC*~GS*PF*LE*~LAI)

Configuration 3 states that core requirements include debt pressure, internal control factors, and governance structure issues. Auxiliary conditions such as profitability and the legal environment showcase the lack of audit independence. Despite maintaining strong internal control measures, operating within environments strictly regulated by external laws, and facing no undue pressures from profitability or debt concerns, unethical financial activities may still occur in this configuration. Governance structure problems granting absolute decision-making power to company controllers render internal controls inactive. Furthermore, absent audit independence diminishes external enforcement efficacy. This configuration frequently leads to scenarios of large shareholders engaging in nepotism and exploiting their power for personal gains. Consider a plausible example where majority shareholders wield actual controlling power, driven by greed to misappropriate funds and jeopardize the interests of minority stakeholders via unauthorized guarantees. Shareholders' persistent commitment to financial fraud furthers corporate governance deficiencies governed by the self-justification dimension of the Fraud Triangle theory. Such a configuration is classified as the "Individual dominant".

(4) Internal-external alliances (DP*~IC*~LE*LAI*GS*~PF)

In Configuration 4, the core prerequisites include debt pressure, audit independence, and governance structure factors, while internal controls and the legal environment exhibit problems. Auxiliary requirements entail profitability issues within the company. This configuration describes the possibility of financial fraud occurring in an enterprise when faced with the combined effects of profitability concerns, internal control issues, and a lack of audit independence. It is widely known that when a listed company records negative net profits for three consecutive years, it faces the risk of delisting. Therefore, even if a company does not have debt problems, if its profitability is not optimistic in the current year, delisting will become its most significant challenge. In this scenario, to avoid bankruptcy and liquidation, the enterprise may resort to shortcut measures. Moreover, internal controls and legal environment issues can facilitate the process of utilizing such measures. In this configuration, the most crucial factors leading to fraudulent activity are internal controls and the legal environment. Although both of these conditions fall within the opportunity dimension of the Fraud Triangle theory, internal controls and profitability serve as endogenous motivators for financial fraud in enterprises, while the legal environment represents an exogenous factor. The interplay between endogenous and exogenous factors drives the occurrence of fraudulent behavior, thus characterizing this configuration as an “Internal-External alliances”.

(5) Pressure-driven (~PF*~DP*~LAI*~IC*~LE)

In Configuration 5, the core prerequisites include profitability and debt problems within the enterprise, as well as the issue of audit independence deficiency. Auxiliary requirements involve internal control and governance structure problems. This configuration reflects that, under pressure, enterprises are susceptible to fraudulent activity. For instance, there is a company that had incurred substantial debt in the past and was facing unfavorable profitability conditions that posed significant obstacles for debt repayment. The situation deteriorated to the point of insolvency where the enterprise's debts exceeded its assets. If a viable solution to facilitate enhanced levels of profitability cannot be effectively implemented, delisting could become an imminent threat. Consequently, the weight of extensive debts would enforce bankruptcy liquidation as the only feasible option. Thus, during periods of extensive external opportunities, such as an absence of audit independence and a relaxed legal environment, management may resort to committing financial fraudulence to tackle existing challenges. The deficiency of internal control effectively nullifies the existence of any

preventive measures against fraudulent activities. Since the core driver behind financial fraudulence under this configuration chiefly stems from pressure generated by profitability and debt-servicing stress, which both attribute to the pressure aspect in the Fraud Triangle theory, it is henceforth titled as "Pressure-Driven".

4.4.Exploring the Five Configurations of Financial Fraudulence

(1) Opportunity-driven

Configuration 1, which is exemplified by Jinzhengda's financial fraud, is best illustrated in their case. Founded in 1998 as a research, production, and sales enterprise specializing in soil products like compound fertilizers, slow-release fertilizers, and soil conditioners, the company's absolute controlling stakeholder was Wan Lianbu with 18.22% ownership, allowing him to have complete dominance over the company. The internal control system regarding Jinzhengda's operations was superficial, with the Board of Supervisors failing to meet its duty responsibilities. There were no objections raised by them in any voting document, including those relating to the firm's finances, production, and operations, related-party transactions, or executive performance. Nevertheless, Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu CPA Ltd. kept partnering with Jinzhengda for many years despite audit fees increasing from 500,000 yuan to 2.35 million yuan between 2010 and 2018. Although profits in 2016 had been falsified almost entirely, auditors gave standard unqualified opinions for three consecutive years, leading to the decade-long concealment of the financial fraud at Jinzhengda due to collusion between their internal controls and audits. Therefore, this incident served as a typical representative of "Opportunity-driven" fraud cases.

(2)Weakly supervised

That path type is exemplified in Configuration 2 and best illustrated by the infamous Kangmei Pharmaceutical fraud case. Established in 1997, Kangmei Pharmaceutical was controlled by its chairman, Ma Xingtian. Although it was once one of the star companies in China's traditional Chinese medicine industry, the surprising fact was that Kangmei Pharmaceutical had repeatedly bribed government officials. For instance, between 2004 and 2013, Ma Xingtian bribed Jiang Jianping, the Deputy mayor of Langzhong city and Deputy Secretary of the Langzhong Municipal Party Committee with HKD 200,000. From 2000 to 2014, he bribed Wan Qingliang, a Standing Committee member of Guangdong Provincial Party Committee and Secretary of the Municipal Party Committee, with HKD 2 million. Between 2014 and 2015, he also bribed Cai Ming, the former Director of the Drug Supervision Department of the Guangdong Provincial Food and Drug Administration, with HKD 300,000. The numerous bribery acts of Ma Xingtian reflect the lax rule of law in the local environment. In addition, starting from 2001, Guangdong Zhongzheng Zhurong Accounting Firm was responsible for Kangmei Pharmaceutical's auditing. In summary, Ma Xingtian's bribery exposes the lenient rule of law in the local area, and the long-term cooperation with the Guangdong Zhongzheng Zhurong Accounting Firm raises issues with audit independence. Therefore, the Kangmei Pharmaceutical fraud case is a typical example of "Weakly supervised" configuration.

(3)Individual dominant

This type of path is exemplified by the notorious Kedi Dairy scandal under Configuration 3. The company belongs to a "family-like" management enterprise, with Zhang Haiqing as the chairman of Kedi Group. Alongside him, Zhang Shaohua (Zhang Haiqing's daughter) serves as the legal person of Kedi Group while his son holds the position of general manager at Kedi Dairy. Furthermore, his wife also plays a key role within the management team, leading to significant issues within Kedi Dairy's internal governance structure. Additionally, the funds obtained through equity collateral by major shareholders were used for related party transactions or fund transfers. Due to a long-standing collaboration with Kedi Dairy, Asia Pacific Accounting Firm became overly reliant on past experience and lacked the necessary professional prudence. Thus, despite adhering to relevant standards for certified accountants, Asia Pacific Accounting Firm failed to exercise due professional skepticism and merely followed customary audit procedures - which did little to detect Kedi Dairy's fraudulent bookkeeping activities. Therefore, the primary cause of the Kedi

Dairy scandal lies in its internal governance structure, characterized by a "Individual dominant" configuration.

(4) Internal-external alliances

The path in question is exemplified by the notorious Dongfang Jinyu fraud case under Condition Configuration 4. The company specializes in wholesale sales of gold, jewelry, and jade raw materials. However, its performance continuously declined from 2015 after being influenced by the Xu Xiang case. Furthermore, the management holds multiple positions, including Zhao Ning who concurrently serves as both the largest shareholder and chairman/general manager, leading to low levels of internal control. Therefore, fraudulent accounting behavior was induced by both internal factors, namely internal control and profit-making ability. In addition, external factors also contributed due to the legal environment. Despite being established in Shenzhen, China, Dongfang Jinyu's main center for financial fraud - led by Sun Gongjie and Hong Ning - was located on an undeveloped island in Yunnan province, beyond the reach of Shenzhen's law enforcement level. Consequently, the Dongfang Jinyu fraud case emerged as a result of the combined action of internal and external factors, consistent with the features of the "Internal-external alliances" configuration.

(5) Pressure-driven

This type of configuration is exemplified in Condition Configuration 5, with the most representative case being the Luckin Coffee fraud scandal. Luckin Coffee has been surrounded by legend since its inception. Initially, it opened up a blue ocean market for "affordable coffee," and then went public in just 17 months. However, after going public, the once-thriving company was hit by a scandal involving falsification of financial records. Following the departure of Lu Zhengyao and Qian Zhiya, we analyzed Luckin Coffee and found that the fraud had been foreseeable. In order to break Starbucks' monopoly on the Chinese market, Luckin chose to take the path of burning cash from the beginning of its IPO. Firstly, in order to attract customers, Luckin Coffee distributed a large number of discount coupons and invested a huge amount of money in advertising. Secondly, the rise in raw material prices further added enormous pressure to Luckin's financial chain. Lastly, rapid expansion led to the rupture of the financial chain. In 2020, Lu Zhengyao used his stocks as collateral to borrow USD 530 million. Therefore, the immense debt pressure and profitability issues were the main factors inducing Luckin to engage in financial fraud, consistent with the characteristics of the "Pressure-driven" configuration."

5. Conclusions and suggestions

This paper employs the fsQCA method, utilizing the Fraud Triangle Theory as the foundation, to scrutinize the joint effects of inducements for corporations to engage in financial fraud. The principal findings of this study are as follows:

(1) A single factor does not constitute a necessary condition for companies to engage in financial fraud, as neither profitability, debt pressure, internal control, legal and environmental governance, lack of audit independence, nor governance capability singularly incite corporations to commit financial reporting malfeasances.

(2) The interaction among multiple conditions results in five configurations that easily lead to financial fraud, namely: opportunity-driven configuration with more opportunities for fraudulent activities; Weakly supervised configuration where external oversight is lax; Individual dominant configuration where managers dominate and have significant control; Internal-external alliances configuration with abundant internal fraudulent opportunities and low likelihood of external exposure; and Pressure-driven configuration where both profit and debt pressures propel the company towards malfeasance.

Hence, utilizing the method of fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis, this paper has derived five routes that are most prone to fraudulent misconduct. Based on this premise, the following recommendations are put forth for identifying and preventing financial malfeasance. Firstly, in regards to opportunity-driven

configuration, external stakeholders should increase their scrutiny towards such firms especially when the management holds multiple roles and has long-standing collaborations with the same accounting firm. The concerned accounting firm is also obliged to exercise professional prudence. Secondly, with regards to weakly supervised configuration, there must be an enhanced focus on the development of external legal framework, coupled with an increase in law enforcement capabilities and efficacy. Thirdly, in terms of individual-dominated configuration, the most crucial aspect would be to optimize one's own governance structure and prevent centralization of power in a single individual, thereby decreasing the likelihood of fraudulent activities. Fourthly, for the internal-external alliances configuration, the internal control level should be elevated while external legal framework construction should be strengthened. Fifthly, to address pressure-driven configurations, companies must adjust their development strategies and maintain an appropriate debt level.

References

- i. Bologna G. Jack, Lindquist Robert J. *Fraud Auditing and Forensic Accounting* [M]. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. 1987.
- ii. W. Steve Albrecht, Wernz, Timothy. *Fraud: Bring the light to the dark side of business* [J]. Irwin Professional Pub. 1995:56-60.
- iii. Bologna G. Jack, Wells Joseph T. *The Accountant's Handbook of Fraud and Commercial Crime* [M]. John Wiley & Sons Inc, 1993. 20-81.
- iv. Bologna G J, Linquist R J. *Fraud Auditing and Forensic Accounting: New Tools and Techniques*. Wiley, 1995.
- v. Parlindungan, Ricardo, Africano, et al. *Financial Statement Fraud Detection Using Published Data Based on Fraud Triangle Theory* [J]. *Advanced Science Letters*, 2017.
- vi. Wu, C.C., Chen, L.L.. *Research on the identification of financial reporting fraud in agricultural listed companies based on fraud triangle theory* [J]. *Finance and Accounting Monthly*, 2015(15):3-7.
- vii. Lin B, Huang JQ, Tan Suxian. *Anti-fraud portrait of Chinese enterprises--an analysis based on fraud triangle theory* [J]. *Finance and Accounting Monthly*, 2022(07):17-25.
- viii. Zhang LJ, Luo ZJ. *Screening methods of business performance evaluation indicators of listed companies* [J]. *Statistics and Decision Making*, 2008(18):63-65.
- ix. Hogan Chris E., Rezaee Zabihollah, Riley Richard A. Jr., Velury Uma K.. *Financial Statement Fraud: Insights from the Academic Literature* [J]. *AUDITING: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 2008, 27(2).
- x. Hu, H. F., Bai, Z. H., Wang, A. P.. *The influence of rule of law environment on corporate fraud and its mechanism of action* [J]. *Study and Practice*, 2022(12):78-90.
- xi. Yu Qian. *Motivations and hazards of accounting fraud in listed companies* [J]. *Science and technology information*, 2016, 14(23):64+66.
- xii. Du Yunzhou, Jia Liangding. *Group perspective and qualitative comparative analysis (QCA): a new path for management research* [J]. *Management World*, 2017(06):155-167.
- xiii. Zhang M., Du Y. Zhou. *The application of QCA methods in organization and management research: orientation, strategy and direction* [J]. *Journal of Management*, 2019, 16(09):1312-1323.
- xiv. Rihoux, D.B., and C.C. Ragin. *Configurational Comparative Methods: Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) and Related Techniques* [M]. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 2009.
- xv. QIN Y. J., YANG J., 2020, *Influence of the configuration effect of environment and organizational factors on the innovation of information technology enterprises - Qualitative comparative analysis based on fuzzy set*, *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, 38(6): 6765-6775.
- xvi. FISS P C. *Building better causal theories: a fuzzy set approach to typologies in organization research* [J]. 2):393-420.